

**BUSINESS CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING. CASE STUDY - COMPARISON
BULGARIA AND KOSOVO**

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Abstract

This paper seeks to examine the challenges facing businesses in implementing social media marketing, to show customers' perceptions, attitudes and perspectives on social media marketing and online shopping for both countries. The survey is based on primary data that include the results derived from questionnaires between Bulgaria and Kosovo conducted with clients and businesses, so to achieve the objectives and research questions we used the quantitative method. In total there are 120 customers respondents and there are 74 businesses respondents.

Both countries have similarities and differences in terms of the challenges they face: businesses in both countries largely use social media to do marketing; the challenge for businesses in both countries is the lack of qualified staff on social media marketing, which then results in not segmenting the market according to demographics; customers of both countries with high income have a greater tendency to make online shopping than those with lower incomes; but there is a big difference between the two countries in the context of functioning in international markets, also a big difference between the two countries in the realization of online sales. The main limitations in the survey are: the number of samples included in the research and not categorization of products according to function but the treatment of online shopping in general.

Based on the research conducted with clients, we conclude that in Bulgaria and Kosovo clients use social media almost equally and the time they spend with social media is similarly distributed between the two countries. However, the tendency to make online purchases is not the same between the two countries, so there is a big difference between them. Customers in Bulgaria have a greater tendency to make online purchases compared to customers in Kosovo.

Keywords: social media marketing, businesses, customers, online shopping

Abstrakt

Dieses Papier versucht, die Herausforderungen zu untersuchen, denen Unternehmen bei der Implementierung von Social Media Marketing gegenüberstehen, um die Wahrnehmungen, Einstellungen und Perspektiven der Kunden zu Social Media Marketing und Online-Shopping für beide Länder aufzuzeigen. Die Umfrage basiert auf Primärdaten, die die Ergebnisse von Fragebögen umfassen, die zwischen Bulgarien und dem Kosovo mit Kunden und Unternehmen durchgeführt wurden. Um die Ziele und Forschungsfragen zu erreichen, haben wir die quantitative Methode verwendet. Insgesamt sind 120 Kunden und 74 Unternehmen befragt worden.

Beide Länder weisen Ähnlichkeiten und Unterschiede hinsichtlich der Herausforderungen auf, mit denen sie konfrontiert sind: Unternehmen in beiden Ländern nutzen Social Media weitgehend für ihr Marketing; die Herausforderung für Unternehmen in beiden Ländern ist der Mangel an qualifiziertem

Personal für Social Media Marketing , was dann dazu führt, dass der Markt nicht nach demografischen Gesichtspunkten segmentiert wird; Kunden beider Länder mit hohem Einkommen neigen stärker zum Online-Shopping als Kunden mit niedrigerem Einkommen; aber es gibt einen großen Unterschied zwischen den beiden Ländern im Zusammenhang mit dem Funktionieren auf internationalen Märkten, auch einen großen Unterschied zwischen den beiden Ländern bei der Realisierung von Online-Verkäufen. Die Haupteinschränkungen in der Umfrage sind: die Anzahl der in die Untersuchung einbezogenen Stichproben und nicht die Kategorisierung der Produkte nach ihrer Funktion, sondern die Behandlung des Online-Shoppings im Allgemeinen.

Auf der Grundlage der mit den Kunden durchgeführten Untersuchungen kommen wir zu dem Schluss, dass in Bulgarien und im Kosovo die Kunden soziale Medien fast gleich häufig nutzen und dass die Zeit, die sie mit sozialen Medien verbringen, in beiden Ländern ähnlich verteilt ist. Allerdings ist die Tendenz zu Online-Einkäufen in den beiden Ländern nicht gleich, so dass ein großer Unterschied zwischen beiden Ländern besteht. Kunden in Bulgarien haben eine größere Neigung zu Online-Einkäufen als Kunden im Kosovo.

Stichworte: social media marketing, unternehmen, kunden, online - shopping

Résumé

Ce document vise à examiner les défis auxquels sont confrontées les entreprises dans la mise en œuvre du marketing des médias sociaux, afin de montrer les perceptions, les attitudes et les perspectives des clients sur le marketing des médias sociaux et les achats en ligne pour les deux pays. L'enquête est basée sur des données primaires qui incluent les résultats dérivés de questionnaires entre la Bulgarie et le Kosovo menés auprès de clients et d'entreprises. Pour atteindre les objectifs et les questions de recherche, nous avons donc utilisé la méthode quantitative. Au total, 120 clients et 74 entreprises ont répondu à l'enquête.

Les deux pays présentent des similitudes et des différences en termes de défis à relever : les entreprises des deux pays utilisent largement les médias sociaux pour faire du marketing ; le défi pour les entreprises des deux pays est le manque de personnel qualifié en marketing des médias sociaux, ce qui a pour conséquence de ne pas segmenter le marché en fonction de la démographie ; les clients des deux pays ayant des revenus élevés ont plus tendance à faire des achats en ligne que ceux ayant des revenus plus faibles ; mais il y a une grande différence entre les deux pays dans le contexte du fonctionnement sur les marchés internationaux, et aussi une grande différence entre les deux pays dans la réalisation des ventes en ligne. Les principales limites de l'enquête sont : le nombre d'échantillons inclus dans la recherche et non la catégorisation des produits selon leur fonction mais le traitement des achats en ligne en général.

Sur la base des recherches menées auprès des clients, nous concluons qu'en Bulgarie et au Kosovo, les clients utilisent les médias sociaux de manière presque égale et que le temps qu'ils y consacrent est réparti de manière similaire entre les deux pays. Cependant, la tendance à faire des achats en ligne n'est pas la même entre les deux pays, il y a donc une grande différence entre eux. Les clients en Bulgarie ont une plus grande tendance à faire des achats en ligne que les clients au Kosovo.

Mots-clés: marketing des médias sociaux, entreprises, clients, achats en ligne

Introduction

Just as the use of social media is changing how people live, learn and connect with one another, fundamental shifts are also taking place within businesses with the introduction and use of social media (Jacobsona, Gruzdb and Garcíac, 2020)

Social media growth and popularity have driven companies into social media use (Anandaa, García, & Lambertib, 2016), so social media is becoming both more convenient and more important, leading many companies to use it in external promotions, marketing, customer management, and as an internal channel for employee communications. Marketing realized on social media has received a lot of attention mainly because the attraction rates for social media advertising are more than 55% higher than those for conventional advertising (Seo and Park, 2018).

Seeing the importance and applicability of social media marketing, the paper addresses the theoretical and practical aspects of identifying the challenges facing businesses when doing marketing on social media. It also explores from a customer perspective how social media marketing will be most appropriate, so using these two areas of research will highlight the gap in the demand and supply of social media marketing. Based on this gap we will recommend improving the way you do marketing on social media.

Objectives. According with the purpose of the study, the following objectives have been raised:

1. To identify the challenges facing businesses in implementing social media marketing.
2. To show customers perception, attitude and perspective on social media marketing and online shopping.
3. To measure the dependence between online shopping and demographic variables.

Hypotheses

H₀: There is no statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the demographic variables.

- **H₀₁:** There is no statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the genders.
- **H₀₂:** There is no statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the ages.
- **H₀₃:** There is no statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the levels of education.
- **H₀₄:** There is no statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the incomes.

H: There is statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the demographic variables.

- **H₁:** There is statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the genders.
- **H₂:** There is statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the ages.
- **H₃:** There is statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the levels of education.

- **H₄:** There is statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the incomes.

Methodology. The survey is based on primary data that include the results derived from questionnaires between Bulgaria and Kosovo conducted with clients and businesses, so to achieve the objectives and research questions we used the quantitative method.

The population of this research is separated in two categories, clients and businesses. In total there are 120 customers respondents and there are 74 businesses respondents.

The sample of the research conducted with clients divided by countries are:

- 58 customers from Bulgaria
- 62 customers from Kosovo

The sample of the research conducted with businesses divided by countries are:

- 36 businesses from Bulgaria
- 38 businesses from Kosovo

Instrument reliability analysis is of particular importance, as all analysis and results are derived from it, so to determine instrument reliability we base on the Cronbach alpha coefficient value, which is known as the instrument reliability verification coefficient.

Cronbach's alpha coefficient values for the reliability of the instrument realized with customers is $\alpha = 0.901$. And values for the reliability of the instrument realized with businesses is $\alpha = 0.825$ which implies that the reliability for the both of the instruments is acceptable.

The questionnaires are created through Google Forms and then distributed to the customers and businesses in Bulgaria and Kosovo. Then all the data are analyzed through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

For the presentation of the results, cross-tabulations were conducted for each questions of the questionnaires, to see the changes in the marketing of social media, between the two countries.

Since demographic data is also part of the questionnaire, we will analyze whether online shopping depends on demographic variables. These analyzes are performed through t-test and ANOVA, or Mann Whitney Test and Kruskal Wallis Test, depending on the distribution of data.

Identifying the social media marketing. Marketing through social media is the latest and popular trend in the market. Traditional marketing tools such as TV, newspapers, magazines have been very expensive and cover a limited targeted market. The traditional marketing strategies were based on focusing on specific markets individually (Nadda, Dadwal , & Firdous, 2015).

Social media marketing is used across sectors and refers to “the use of social media technologies, channels, and software to create, communicate, deliver, and exchange offerings that have value for an organization's stakeholders” (Jacobsona, Gruzdb, & Garcíac, 2020). Social media is a recent phenomenon, and marketers and companies already use social media as part of their marketing strategy (Anandaa, Garcíac, & Lambertib, 2016), which helps businesses market their brand to the wider ‘global’ community. Social media platforms are open and accessible to everyone from any country and therefore they offer businesses tremendous opportunities to communicate with communities and build relationships with their target audience (Hyde and Brogan, 2016).

The phenomenon of social media can be explained from three perspectives: **First:** From sociology or anthropology, networks favor interaction between people all around the world. ((Hofacker & Belanche, 2016; Yadav, de Valck, Hennig-Thurau, Hoffman, & Spann, 2013); **Second:** From an economic approach, social media have an important value for the firms that own them, although often users do not pay for these services. (Hofacker & Belanche, 2016; Yadav, de Valck, Hennig-Thurau, Hoffman, & Spann, 2013); **Third:** From a marketing approach, social media function as a market space in which both buyers and sellers exist along with various exchange facilitators all interacting with each other in complex ways. (Hofacker & Belanche, 2016; Yadav, de Valck, Hennig-Thurau, Hoffman, & Spann, 2013).

Social media has changed the basic approach that marketing has in principle. By definition, marketing is a social and managerial process through which individuals and groups benefit from what they need and want through the creation, delivery and exchange of valuable products with others (Kotler & Keller, 2012), whereas social media marketing has actually enabled businesses to get impressions, comments and suggestions from their customers through blogs, photos and ratings and improve their products and services so that customer needs can be addressed in a way more proactive way. So, advertising and marketing have changed completely because of social media (Nadda, Dadwal, & Firdous, 2015).

Social media marketing is a new orientation where businesses are managing to identify target customers. Social media marketing can simply be defined as the use of social media channels to promote a company and its products. (Nadaraja & Yazdanifard, 2013)

This type of marketing can be thought of as a submission of online marketing activities that complement traditional Web-based promotion strategies, such as email newsletters and online advertising campaigns. (Nadaraja & Yazdanifard, 2013; Barefoot & Szabo, 2009).

Social Media Marketing is a completely new way of communication with the consumer. It is also a transition from traditional marketing, where there is one-way communication between a company and its customers (Simon, 2015).

Due to the existence of various factors, social media is the most effective medium in changing brand perception. These factors are:

- **Provides input for the Advertisements:** Social Media can be used to understand the various facilities, items, characteristics and issues that is found in most of the discussions and accordingly these can be used as input for advertising so as to build the brand perception (Tiwari, 2017);
- **Helps in identifying the Targetable audience:** Social media is helpful in identifying the target customers and this can be used to influence the brand perception (Tiwari, 2017);
- **Provides Platform:** Social media provides a platform to increase brand awareness and to reinforce the brands proposition (Tiwari, 2017).
- **Helps to know Consumer's Perception:** The importance of brand largely depends on the perception of the people. It is important to know that perception is a reality (Tiwari, 2017).

If we look at the objectives of social media marketing, these may be listed as increasing sales, increasing brand awareness, improving brand image, managing traffic on online platforms, reducing marketing costs, increasing interaction by encouraging users to share message and content, learning about the views of consumers regarding the firm or the activities of the firm (Gümüş, 2017; Felix, Rauschnabel, & Hinsch, 2017). In addition, social media is a unique platform for marketers to listen to

their customers, what is said about their products by customers and discussion among customers. By doing so, traders can match their marketing activities to customer needs (Helmink, 2013). Additionally, marketers are able to establish two-way communication and interaction with existing and potential customers in a way faster and richer than ever, without any intermediaries ((Gümüş, 2017; Felix, Rauschnabel, & Hinsch, 2017).

Based on this, social media marketing has many advantages. The primary advantages of social media marketing are reducing costs and enhancing reach. The cost of a social media platform is typically lower than other marketing platforms such as face-to face sales people or middlemen or distributors. (Nadaraja & Yazdanifard, 2013). In addition, social media marketing allows firms to reach customers that may not be accessible due to temporal and locational limitations of existing distribution channels (Nadaraja & Yazdanifard, 2013). Social media platforms increase reach and reduce costs by providing three areas of advantage for customers. First, the marketing firm can provide unlimited information to customers without human intervention. Second, social media marketing firm can create interactions by customizing information for individual customers that allow customers to design products and services that meet their specific requirements. (Watson, Pitt, Berthon, & Zinkhan, 2002). Finally, social media platforms can allow transactions between customers and firms that would typically require human contact ((Watson, Pitt, Berthon, & Zinkhan, 2002).

In addition to the advantages, social media marketing also faces challenges and difficulties, creating disadvantages in the application of social media marketing.

The transparency of the web makes online information available to all audiences, and reinforces the need for consistency in the planning, design, implementation and control of online marketing communication (Nadaraja & Yazdanifard, 2013).

Some disadvantages of social media marketing are:

- Social media marketing has the disadvantage that at any time you need to ensure the presence of businesses on social media to give answers to all potential customers and if they are not available at all times to give you answers, then there is a risk that they go to the competition, where there are unlimited offers to make online purchases.
- In marketing realized on social media, it is difficult to measure the success of efforts, it is difficult to measure the effectiveness of brand awareness. There is also the risk of facing negative situations that deviate from reality by damaging the business image and questioning the quality of the products;
- To execute social media marketing, qualified personnel are required, so this makes social media marketing costly;
- The issue of security is another disadvantage that social media marketing faces, so businesses need to secure the social media profiles so that they are not harmed in this way;
- Social media marketing enables business to be very open to competitors, where competition can benefit from the information they receive. It is therefore important to choose what is important to be public and what is not.

Results

Demographic data

From the gender graph, participants in the research conducted in Bulgaria were 53.4% female and 46.6% male. In the research conducted in Kosovo, were 51.5% female and 48.4% male. Based on the percentage, we notice that the percentage of gender distribution between the two countries is very close to each other (see fig. 1).

Figure 1. The cross tabulation of gender between Kosovo and Bulgaria.

Based on the graph, in Bulgaria were 5.2% of respondents in the category 18 - 25 years, 19% of respondents in the category 26 - 33 years, 32.8% in the category 34 - 41 years, 24.1% of respondents in the category 42 - 49 years old, and 19% of respondents were over 50 years old. In the research conducted in Kosovo were 19.4% in the category 18 - 25 years, 32.3% of respondents in the category 26 - 33 years, 22.6% of respondents in the category 34 - 41 years, 17.7% of respondents in the category 42 - 49 years old and only 8.1% were over 50 years old.

Figure 2. The cross tabulation between Kosovo and Bulgaria of age.

(see fig. 2). From the statistics we see that the participants in the research in Kosovo were younger compared to Bulgaria, this may be because the population in Kosovo has an average age of 29.5 years, while the average of age of the population in Bulgaria is 43.4 years.

Based on the graph that shows the level of education, respondents from Bulgaria have this distribution: with primary education no respondents, 17.2% of respondents had secondary education, and 82.8% of respondents had completed bachelor studies. Respondents from Kosovo had this distribution in terms of level of education: 3.2% were with primary education, 19.4% with secondary education, 50% had completed bachelor studies and 27.4% had postgraduate education (see fig. 3).

Figure 3. The cross tabulation education between Kosovo and Bulgaria of level of education.

Figure 4. The cross tabulation between Kosovo and Bulgaria of incomes.

3.4% of respondents from Bulgaria had incomes between 0 - 140 Euro, 1.7% had incomes between 140 - 280 Euro, 15.5% had incomes between 280 - 420 Euro, 48.3% had incomes between 420 - 560 Euro and 31% had incomes over 500 Euro. (see fig. 4). 4.8% of respondents from Kosovo had incomes between 0 - 140 Euro, 3.2% had incomes between 140 - 280 Euro, 38.7% had incomes between 280 - 420 Euro, 16.1% had incomes between 420 - 560 Euro and 37.1% had incomes over 500 Euro.

Customer research

Figure 5. The cross tabulation for the use of social networks between Bulgaria and Kosovo.

Based on the graph, 94.8% of respondents from Bulgaria have been declared that are using social media, while 5.2% do not use social media. While respondents from Kosovo have been declared 100% that they are users of social media (see fig. 5).

Figure 6. The cross tabulation between Bulgaria and Kosovo for the spent time on social media.

In Bulgaria, 15.5% of respondents were answered, that they use social media per day over 4 hours, 13.8% use them 3 to 4 hours per day, 25.9% use them 2 to 3 hours, 32.8% use them 1 to 2 hours per day, and 12.1% use them less than one hour per day. While in Kosovo, the respondents that were answered, 11.3% use social media per day over 4 hours, 17.7% use them 3 to 4 hours per day, 33.9% use them 2 to 3 hours per day and the respondents that use social media less than one hours per day were 11.3%. (see

fig.6)

Figure 7. The cross tabulation between Bulgaria and Kosovo for the reason for using social media.

In terms of why social media is used the most, in Bulgaria 43.1% of customers use social media to be informed, 32.8% use it to spend time and have fun, 22.4% use it to have access with other people, and 1.7% to share opinions and photos with others. In Kosovo 69.4% use social media to be informed about news, 16.1% to spend time and have fun, 11.3% to have access to other people and 3.2% to share opinions and photos with others (see fig. 7).

Figure 8. The cross tabulation for online purchases between Bulgaria and Kosovo.

In survey conducted in Bulgaria, 74.1% of respondents stated that they bought online products and 25.9% of them never bought online products. In Kosovo, 77.4% of respondents bought products, while 22.6% did not. According to the analysis, customers of both countries have a similar tendency to make online purchases. (see fig. 8).

Figure 9. The cross tabulation between Bulgaria and Kosovo for frequency of online shopping.

In Bulgaria, 13.8% of customers say they never make online shopping, 32.8% rarely make online shopping, 25.9% sometimes, 24.1% often, and 3.4% say they always make online shopping. Whereas in Kosovo 19.4% of business customers make online shopping, 37.1% rarely make online shopping, 29% sometimes, 12.9% often and only 1.6% have stated that they always make online shopping. (see fig. 9).

According to the percentages, the frequency of online shopping is similar between the two countries. In Bulgaria 56.9% of respondents are answered, that they purchase 0-20% in online shopping, 29.3% in category 20-40%, 10.3% in category 40-

Figure 10. The cross tabulation between Bulgaria and Kosovo for the percentage of online purchases.

60%, 1.7% in category 60-80% and 1.7% are answered, that 80-100% purchase in online shopping. While in Kosovo 71% of respondents purchase 0-20% in online shopping, 21% answered in category 20-40%, 6.5% in category 40-60%, just 1.6% were in category 60-80% and no one answered in category 80-100% of purchases. (see fig. 10).

Figure 11. The cross tabulation between Bulgaria and Kosovo for knowledge of how ads appear on social media.

In Bulgaria, 62.1% of customers had knowledge of how ads appeared on social media, and 37.9% had no knowledge. In Kosovo, 66.1% of customers had knowledge of how ads appeared on social media and 33.9% had no knowledge. So, the clients of both countries were approximately the same informed about the appearance of ads on social media (see fig. 11).

Figure 12. The cross tabulation between Bulgaria and Kosovo for the level of satisfaction of ads that appear on social media.

In Bulgaria 17.2% of customers were very dissatisfied with the ads that appear on social media, 31% dissatisfied, 1.7% remained neutral on this issue, 50% satisfied. In Kosovo, 12.9% of customers were very dissatisfied with the ads that appear on social media, 30.6% dissatisfied, 50% remained neutral regarding this issue, 4.8% satisfied and only 1.6% were very satisfied (see fig.11). According to statistics, there is a big difference in customer satisfaction between the two countries with the ads that appears on social media, where we see that the most dissatisfied are customers from Kosovo. (see fig. 12).

In Bulgaria 36.2% of customers were strongly disagree to use their personal data to display ads according to their personal interest, 50% were disagree, 12.1% were undecided and only 1.7% were strongly agree see fig. 12). In Kosovo 29% of customers were strongly disagree to use their personal data to display ads according to their personal interest, 22.6% were disagree, 38.7 % were undecided and only 1.6% were strongly agree. (see fig. 13).

Figure 13. The cross-tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo on the degree of compliance in the use of personal data for the presentation of ads according to personal

Verification of hypotheses

According to the results of the analysis, in Bulgaria the average of participant's male is 2.74 and females is 2.68. So, both of genders have stated that sometimes make online shopping. In Kosovo, the average of participant's male is 2.47 and for females is 2.34. So, both of genders have expressed that they sometimes make online shopping (see table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for online shopping by gender. Source: own survey, 2020.

Country	Group Statistics					
		Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Bulgaria	Online shopping	Male	27	2.74	0.903	0.174
		Female	31	2.68	1.249	0.224
Kosovo		Male	30	2.47	1.074	0.196
		Female	32	2.34	0.937	0.166

Based on the gender of the two countries, we see that there is no significant difference between the groups.

In the research conducted in Bulgaria, also the result of Sig (2 - tailed) where $p = 0.828 > 0.05$ shows that there is no significant difference between the groups average. In the research conducted in Kosovo, the result of Sig (2 - tailed) where $p = 0.632 > 0.05$ shows that there is no significant difference between the group averages. Based on the significance for both states, we accept the null hypothesis which states that there is no statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the genders.

Table 2. T - test for dependence of online purchases by gender. Source: own survey, 2020.

Independent Samples Test											
Country			Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
			F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
										Lower	Upper
Bulgaria	Online shopping	Equal variances assumed	5.61	0.02	0.21	56	0.828	0.06	0.29	-0.51	0.64
		Equal variances not assumed			0.22	54.26	0.824	0.06	0.28	-0.50	0.63
Equal variances assumed		0.72	0.39	0.48	60	0.632	0.12	0.25	-0.38	0.63	
Equal variances not assumed				0.48	57.67	0.634	0.12	0.25	-0.39	0.64	
Kosovo											

Before the ANOVA test was performed, it was verified whether the data met the condition for normal distribution and homogeneity of variance between ages. Thus, Levene's test for variance homogeneity between groups turned out to be greater than $p > 0.05$, indicating that the variances are the same for all age groups and that the results obtained from the analysis of variance are reliable for both countries (see table 2).

According to the ANOVA test we confirm the null hypothesis which says that there is no statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the ages based on $p > 0.05$ for both states (for Bulgaria $p = 0.08$ and for Kosovo $p = 0.673$).

Table 3. ANOVA for dependence of online shopping by age. Source: own survey, 2020.

ANOVA							
Country			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Bulgaria	Online shopping	Between Groups	9.524	4	2.381	2.157	0.086
		Within Groups	58.493	53	1.104		
		Total	68.017	57			
Kosovo		Between Groups	2.414	4	0.603	0.588	0.673
		Within Groups	58.506	57	1.026		
		Total	60.919	61			

Before performing the ANOVA test, variance homogeneity (Levene's test: sig: $p > .05$) and normal data distribution were confirmed.

According to the ANOVA test we confirm the null hypothesis which says that there is no statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the levels of education based on $p > 0.05$ for both states (for Bulgaria $p = 0.198$ and for Kosovo $p = 0.163$).

Table 4. ANOVA for dependence of online purchases by level of education. Source: own survey, 2020.

ANOVA								
Country	Online shopping		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Bulgaria		Between Groups		2.001	1	2.001	1.697	0.198
		Within Groups		66.017	56	1.179		
		Total		68.017	57			
Kosovo		Between Groups		5.111	3	1.704	1.771	0.163
		Within Groups		55.809	58	0.962		
	Total		60.919	61				

Initially homogeneity of variance (Levene's test: sig: $p > .05$) and normal data distribution were confirmed.

From ANOVA results show that there is a statistically significant relationship between different income groups and online shopping, based on $p < 0.05$. So, in this case, we refuse the zero hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, because according to the analysis we came to the conclusion that there is statistically significant interrelation that online shopping manifests differently between the incomes. So, customers who have higher incomes have a greater tendency to make online shopping.

Table 5. ANOVA for dependence of online purchases by incomes. Source: own survey, 2020.

ANOVA								
Country	Online shopping		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Bulgaria		Between Groups		17.271	4	4.318	4.510	0.003
		Within Groups		50.746	53	0.957		
		Total		68.017	57			
Kosovo		Between Groups		2.934	4	0.733	0.721	0.001
		Within Groups		57.986	57	1.017		
	Total		60.919	61				

Businesses research

Figure 14. The cross-tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for number of employees.

Part of the research were 58.3% Bulgarian businesses that have 0 - 9 employees, 19.4% with 10 - 49 employees and 22.2% businesses with over 250 employees. In Kosovo, there were 73.7% businesses with 0 - 9 employees, 21.1% with 10 - 49 employees and 5.3% with 50 - 249 employees (see fig. 14).

Figure 15. The cross-tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for operation in international markets.

In Bulgaria, 61.1% of businesses operate in international markets and 38% do not. In Kosovo, 28.9% of businesses operate in international markets and 71.1% do not. According to the research results, there is a big difference in terms of operation in international markets between the two countries. Bulgarian business operates more in international markets than Kosovar businesses (see fig. 15).

Figure 16. The cross-tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for the percentage of sales made internationally.

In Bulgaria, 47.2% of respondents are answered that they have 0-20% of their sales in international market, 22.2% are answered that their sales in international market are 20-40%, 5.6% respondents have their sales in international market, about 40-60% of total sales, Also 5.6% other respondents are answered that their sales in international market are 60-80%, and 19.4% of respondents, almost all sales do internationally, with a share about 80-100% of total sales (see fig. 16). While in Kosovo, 84.2% of respondents almost all sales do in domestic market, just 0-20% of sales do internationally,

10.5% answered that their sales in the international market are about 20-40% of total sales. Just 2.6% of respondents answered that their sales are 40-60% internationally, also 2.6% of respondents are answered that they do their sales almost totally in international market.

Figure 17. The cross-tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for making online sales.

In Bulgaria, businesses reported 63.9% who sell online and 36.1% do not sell online. In Kosovo, 28.9% of businesses make online sales and 71.1% state that they do not make online purchases (see fig. 17).

The graph shows a difference between the two countries in terms of online sales, where businesses in Bulgaria tend to make more online sales than traditional sales. While in Kosovo it is the complete opposite, businesses sell more in the traditional way than in online way.

Figure 18. The cross - tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for the percentage of sales made online.

Figure 19. The cross - tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for using social media to do marketing.

Figure 20. The cross - tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for percent of using social media to do marketing.

In Bulgaria 58.8% of respondents are answered, that they sale 0-20% in online way, 23.5% of them sell online about 20-40% of total sales, just 2.9% of respondents sell in online way about 40-60% of total sales, and 14.7% answered that they almost sell online with the share 80-100% of total sales. While in Kosovo 86.8% of respondents sell in online just 0-20% of total sales, 7.9% of them sell online about 20-40% and 5.3% answered that they sell online 40-60% of total sales (see fig. 18).

In Bulgaria, of all the businesses surveyed, 86.1% said they use social media to do marketing and only 13.9% do not. In Kosovo, 89.5% of businesses use social media to do marketing and 10.5% of them do not use it. According to statistics we see that businesses in Bulgaria and Kosovo are more oriented to do social media marketing (see fig. 19).

In Bulgaria, 44.4% of companies answered that use marketing in social networks just 0 - 20% of marketing activities, 27.8% of respondents answered that use marketing in social networks about 20 - 40% of their marketing activities, 8.3% have used social networks for marketing activities from 40 - 60% of total marketing activities, just 5.6% of respondents answered that use 60 - 80% of marketing in social networks, and 13.9% of respondents answered that almost all of marketing activities have concentrated in social networks, while in Kosovo, 24.3% of companies answered that use marketing in social

networks just 0 - 20% of their marketing activities, 13.5% of respondents answered that use marketing in social networks about 20 - 40% of theirs marketing activities, 29.7% of them answered that use 40 - 60% of marketing in social networks, 18.9% of respondents use marketing activities in social networks from 60

- 80% of their activities, and 13.5% are answered that almost their marketing activities have concentrated in social networks (see fig. 20).

Figure 21. Cross - tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for distribution of choosing Social Media for doing Marketing.

The choosing of the social media to do marketing by companies in Bulgaria are: Facebook with 16.57%, Pinterest with 17.68%, YouTube with 18.78%, Twitter with 19.34%, Instagram with 15.57%, Tumblr with 12.15%, Reddit and other social media with 0%. The choosing of the social media to do marketing by companies in Kosovo are: Facebook with 16.44%, Pinterest with 10.96%, YouTube with 15.07%, Twitter with 12.33%, Instagram with 13.70%, Tumblr with 8.22%, Reddit with 9.58% and other social media with 13.70% (see fig. 21).

Figure 22. Cross - tabulations between Bulgaria and Kosovo for distribution of Social Media Marketing.

Both Bulgarian and Kosovar businesses responded that they mostly use Facebook to do marketing in social media. Facebook is used by Bulgarians with 27.24%, while in Kosovars with 31.35% of businesses. Instagram is used by Bulgarians with 17.19%, while Kosovars with 25.99% of businesses. Pinterest is used

by Bulgarians with 16.78%, while in Kosovars only 9.17% of businesses. YouTube is used by Bulgarians with 15.96%, while in Kosovo 7.65% of businesses. Twitter is used by Bulgaria with 13.48%, while in Kosovo with 6.88% of businesses. Tumblr is used by Bulgarians with 9.35%, while Kosovars with 6.57% of businesses. Reddit is used by Kosovars with 6.27%, while Bulgarian with 0% of businesses. And the other social media are used by Kosovars with 6.12%, while Bulgarian with 0% of businesses (see fig. 22). As, it is presented in figure 21 and 22, there is a difference between how the businesses choose the social media and how much the businesses share the percentage of doing marketing in social media. The choose is shared in more social media, but the percentage of doing marketing is more in Facebook for both of countries, and Instagram is more in Kosovars businesses.

According to the research results, 39.5% of businesses in both countries never segment the market according to demographics, 7.9% rarely, 18.4% sometimes, 13.3% often and 10.5% always (see fig. 23).

Figure 23. Segmentation of the market.

In research conducted in Bulgaria and Kosovo, just some businesses have qualified staff for social media marketing. Of the businesses surveyed, 21.1% had qualified staff for social media marketing and 78.9% did not (fig. 24).

Figure 24. The existence of qualified staff for social media marketing.

According to the research results, 34.2% of businesses choose social media to do marketing by number of users, 2.6% by price per click, 15.8% according to the use of social network for the specific segment of clients, 18.4% were for the option according to all of the above, 26.3% were for the none of the above option (fig. 25).

Figure 25. The ways of choosing to do marketing in social media.

Conclusions and Recommendation

Based on the research conducted with clients, we conclude that in Bulgaria and Kosovo clients use social media almost equally and the time they spend with social media is similarly distributed between the two countries. However, the tendency to make online purchases is not the same between the two countries, so there is a big difference between them. Customers in Bulgaria have a greater tendency to make online purchases compared to customers in Kosovo.

Regarding the knowledge of customers about the way of presenting advertisements on social media, we come to the conclusion that customers of both countries have considerable knowledge and at approximate levels of how advertisements are presented on social media. They were also against giving their personal data so that the advertisements could be presented to you according to the personal interests of each client. This is why customers are largely unhappy with the ads that appear to you on their social networks.

Based on business research, there is a big difference between the two countries in the context of operating in international markets where Bulgarian businesses operate more than Kosovar businesses in international markets. There is also a big difference between the two countries in the realization of online sales, which shows that businesses in Bulgaria have a greater tendency to realize online sales than businesses in Kosovo.

Despite the difference between the two countries in the realization of online sales, this difference does not exist in the use of social media to do marketing, which means that social media marketing is largely used by businesses in both countries.

According to the analysis, we conclude that the challenge for businesses is the lack of qualified staff on social media marketing, which then consequently has market non segmentation the market according to demographics but finding another way to do marketing. This could be the wrong path which will directly affect the number of online sales or traditional sales as well. The reason why market segmentation is important is because according to tests it has been found that customers with higher incomes have a greater tendency to make online shopping compared to those with lower incomes. So,

online shopping is in direct proportion to incomes, where with the growth of one grows the other or vice versa.

Although according to statistical tests it has shown that other demographic variables such as gender, age and level of education tend to make the same online purchases, this is in general for online purchases, but not for different categories of products which are shared based on preference of demographic categories.

Based on these conclusions, we recommend that any business that claims to do social media marketing have qualified staff for social media marketing, because the lack of these employees to do marketing on social media will increase the cost of marketing for clients. Market segmentation according to demographics and customer preferences is the only way that social media marketing is carried out in the right way, thus increasing sales.

Given that in Kosovo businesses conduct much less online sales than businesses in Bulgaria, we recommend that problems be identified that make online sales smaller than traditional sales.

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